

Search for Potent Anthelmintics Part I: Substituted Quinolinoyl Hydrazines, Semicarbazides and Thiosemicarbazides

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Manuscript received 13 November 1971; revised 3 April 1972; accepted 14 November 1972

Some 3-methyl-4-hydroxy-6- or 8-substituted-2-quinolinoyl hydrazines and N_1 -(3-methyl-4-hydroxy-6 or 8-substituted-2-quinolinoyl)-4-aryl or cyclohexyl thiosemicarbazides and semicarbazides have been synthesized with a view to evaluating their anthelmintic activity.

The 2-carbethoxy-3-methyl-4-hydroxy-6 or 8-substituted quinolines were condensed with hydrazine hydrate to yield hydrazines which on condensation with aryl or cyclohexyl isothiocyanates or phenyl isocyanate afforded the desired thiosemicarbazides or semicarbazides respectively.

SOME 3-methyl-4-hydroxy-6 or 8-substituted-2-quinolinoyl hydrazines and N_1 -(3-methyl-4-hydroxy-6 or 8-substituted-2-quinolinoyl)-4-aryl or cyclohexyl thiosemicarbazides and semicarbazides have been synthesized with a view to evaluating their anthelmintic activity.

Recently several hydrazides^{1,2}, isothiocyanates³ thiocarbanilides⁴ and 4-substituted quinolines^{5,6} were found to possess excellent anthelmintic activity. This prompted us to synthesise the title compounds with the idea that the combined effect of the quinoline nucleus and >N-C- or >N-C- group might

confer much enhanced anthelmintic activity on these compounds. The intermediate hydrazines are also expected to exhibit marked anthelmintic activity.

The 2-carbethoxy-3-methyl-4-hydroxy-6 or 8-substituted quinolines prepared by the method of Edgar⁷ were condensed with hydrazine hydrate to yield corresponding hydrazines. The latter on condensation with aryl or cyclohexyl isothiocyanates or

phenyl isocyanate afforded the desired thiosemicarbazides or semicarbazides respectively.

The anthelmintic activity of these compounds will be reported later on.

Experimental

I. 3-Methyl-4-hydroxy-6 or 8-substituted-2-quinolinoyl hydrazines :

2-carbethoxy-3-methyl-4-hydroxy-6 or 8-substituted quinoline (0.01 mole) and hydrazine hydrate 98% (0.015 mole) were taken in a 100 ml r.b. flask, 25 ml of absolute ethanol was added and the mixture refluxed for 3 hr on a steam bath. The solvent was removed. The solid obtained was washed with little water and recrystallised from 80% ethanol.

The analytical data are given in Table 1.

II. N_1 -(3-methyl-4-hydroxy-6- or 8-substituted-2-quinolinoyl)-4-aryl or cyclohexyl thiosemicarbazides and semicarbazides :—

TABLE I

Sl. No.	R	m.p.* °C	Yield %	Formula	Percentage Analysis					
					Calculated			Found		
					C	H	N	C	H	N
1.	8-CH ₃	245	86	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂	62.33	5.62	18.18	62.24	5.90	17.82
2.	8-OCH ₃	250	85	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₃	58.29	5.22	17.00	58.10	5.50	16.81
3.	6-OCH ₃	> 260	85	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₃	58.29	5.22	17.00	58.52	5.43	16.60

* All melting points are uncorrected.

TABLE 2

Sl. No.	X	R	R ₁	m.p.* °C	Yield %	Formula	% N	
							Calc.	Found
1.	S	8-CH ₃	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	224—226	90	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ ClN ₄ O ₃ S	13.98	13.79
2.	"	"	<i>p</i> -bromophenyl	227—228	91	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ BrN ₄ O ₃ S	12.36	12.13
3.	"	"	Phenyl	218—219	90	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃ S	15.30	15.59
4.	"	"	Cyclohexyl	234—235	70	C ₁₉ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₃ S	15.05	14.95
5.	"	8-OCH ₃	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	229—230	88	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ ClN ₄ O ₃ S	13.44	13.10
6.	"	"	<i>p</i> -bromophenyl	224—225	86	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ BrN ₄ O ₃ S	12.14	11.90
7.	"	"	α -naphthyl	221—222	85	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃ S	12.96	12.62
8.	"	"	Phenyl	222	89	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃ S	14.65	14.25
9.	"	"	Cyclohexyl	247	70	C ₁₉ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₃ S	14.58	14.31
10.	"	6-OCH ₃	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	224	86	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ ClN ₄ O ₃ S	13.44	13.01
11.	"	"	<i>p</i> -bromophenyl	230	88	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ BrN ₄ O ₃ S	12.14	12.49
12.	"	"	α -naphthyl	218—219	85	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃ S	12.96	12.71
13.	"	"	Phenyl	270	89	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃ S	14.65	14.55
14.	O	8-CH ₃	Phenyl	215	90	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃	16.00	15.70
15.	"	8-OCH ₃	Phenyl	217	90	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₄	15.30	15.01

* All melting points are uncorrected.

Equimolar proportions of 3-methyl-4-hydroxy-6 or 8-substituted 2-quinolinoyl hydrazine and aryl or cyclohexyl isothiocyanates or isocyanates were taken in dry benzene and the mixture refluxed for 1 hr on a steam bath. The solid separated on cooling was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

Compounds prepared are reported in Table 2.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank Dr. Ram Gopal, Professor and Head of the Chemistry Department, Lucknow University for providing the departmental facilities and Dr. Kirpa Shanker for helpful discussions. The

authors are also grateful to the State C.S.I.R. (U.P.) for the award of contingent grant to one of them (M.I.H.).

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